

1 **Title:** SPORT AS COGNITION ENHANCER FROM CHILDHOOD TO
2 YOUNG ADULTHOOD: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW FOCUSED ON
3 SPORT MODALITY

4 **Authors:** Alejandro Gutiérrez-Capote^{1,2}, Jesús Jiménez-Martínez^{1,2}, Iker
5 Madinabeitia^{1,2*}, María de Orbe-Moreno^{1,2}, Caterina Pesce³, David Cardenas^{1,2}

6 ¹*Faculty of Sports Science, Department of Physical Education and Sport, University of*
7 *Granada, Spain.*

8 ²*Sport and Health University Research Institute (iMUDS), Granada, Spain.*

9 ³*University of Rome “Foro Italico”, Department of Movement, Human and Health*
10 *Sciences, Rome, Italy*

11 **Corresponding author:**

12 Iker Madinabeitia

13 Department of Physical Education and Sport, Faculty of Sport Sciences, University of
14 Granada, Carretera de Alfacar s/n. 18071 Granada, Spain.

15 Phone number: +34 958244375.

16 E-mail: ikermadi@ugr.es

17 **Keywords**

18 Sport modality, cognition, executive functions, acute effect, chronic effect.

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28 **Abstract**

29 **This systematic review aims** to synthesize the cognitive effects of different sports. The
30 major novelty **is** represented by a nuanced distinction of sport modalities beyond the
31 open-closed skills dichotomy and **a focus on interventional research to address causality**
32 **linking sport practice to transient and longer-lasting cognitive outcomes** in acute and
33 chronic sport intervention designs, **respectively**. Four research databases (Web of
34 Science, PubMed (MEDLINE), Scopus, and SportDiscus) were searched for studies
35 reporting on acute and chronic interventions focused on sports and performed with
36 participants between 6 and 25 years old. A total of 30 studies met our inclusion criteria.
37 Overall, single bouts of sport-based activities and extended sports training interventions
38 generate benefits in various cognitive outcome domains. Such benefits vary among
39 cognitive outcomes and between acute and chronic designs, depending on the specific
40 sport modality.

41 Introduction

42 A rising **number** of partially overlapping systematic reviews and meta-analyses of studies
43 investigating the effects of physical activity (PA) on cognition have been published in
44 recent years, **with conclusions of** overall positive effects (Erickson et al., 2019), **or no**
45 **effects** (Ciria et al., 2022) and **calls for a more nuanced understanding** of moderators
46 acting on the PA-cognition relation (Ludyga et al., 2020; Pesce, Vazou, et al., 2021).

47 The nuances of this relationship **have also been explored, though less frequently,**
48 in the specific context of sports practice, in which only a few recent quantitative
49 (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2021; Heilmann et al., 2022) and qualitative (Gu et al., 2019;
50 Shi et al., 2022) reviews have provided initial syntheses. In the past decade, the research
51 focus has shifted from sport-specific cognition, such as the ability to make tactical
52 decisions in sports games, to higher-order, domain-general cognition (Voss et al., 2010).
53 Therefore, this review aims to build upon existing evidence of the effects of practicing
54 sports on higher-order, domain-general cognitive functions.

55 Within a broad array of definitions of higher-order cognition, one that can
56 reconcile divergences encompasses voluntary and highly effortful domain-general
57 multidimensional control processes contributing to goal-directed actions (Kosslyn &
58 Ochsner, 2013). When applied to research on the effects of sport on cognition, this
59 construct definition must be further differentiated according to the level of domain
60 generality vs. sport specificity of assessment tasks, stimuli used, and responses captured.
61 **To characterize domain general cognition the assessments should not involve sports-**
62 **specific stimuli or skills** (Kalén et al., 2021).

63 The existing reviews on the sport-cognition relation during the developmental
64 years have outlined a general cognitive advantage related to sports practice in children
65 and adolescents (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2021). This advantage might be explained by

66 referring to the fact that sport practice couples the metabolic-physiological demands of
67 physical exercise with the cognitive engagement needed in sports to learn new movement
68 skills and, in open-skills sports, to cope with situational uncertainty.

69 The mechanisms proposed to underlie the effects of the physical component of
70 PA and sports practice are primarily the elevation of circulating levels of neurotrophic
71 factors (neurotrophic stimulation hypothesis; Walsh et al., 2020) and of overall
72 cerebrovascular function (cardiovascular fitness hypothesis; Agbangla et al., 2021).
73 Circulating neurotrophins may be transiently elevated within a single bout of PA (**acute**
74 **effects**) and then prolongedly along a training program (**chronic effects**; El-Sayes et al.,
75 2019). In contrast, cardiovascular fitness gains may be achieved only with a protracted
76 training program. Also, motor **skill** learning is an inherent feature of sports training that
77 promotes brain plasticity (Marcori & Okazaki, 2019) and cognitive function (Moreau et
78 al., 2015), **and** has been proposed as a mechanism that underlies the beneficial effects on
79 high-level, domain-general cognition (Pesce et al., 2019; Tomporowski & Pesce, 2019).
80 Moreover, the impact of sports training on higher-level cognitive functions is likely due
81 also to the level of cognitive challenge posed by the sport actions. This is referred to as
82 the ‘cognitive stimulation hypothesis’, which assumes that there are physical activities,
83 as given sport modalities, which are inherently cognitively challenging (Heilmann et al.,
84 2022).

85 The most common distinction made in both cross-sectional and interventional
86 studies to identify whether the demands of different sport modalities moderate the effects
87 of sports practice and expertise on cognition is between closed-skill sports (CSS) and
88 open-skill sports (OSS). Sports can be qualified according to their practice stability and
89 predictability. In OSS (e.g., football), athletes play in variable and unpredictable
90 environments and have to react to changing situations, while in CSS (e.g., gymnastics),

91 athletes have more consistent and self-paced conditions. There is consistent evidence,
92 especially among cross-sectional studies, that high-level cognition is superior in athletes
93 who are experienced in OSS (Gu et al., 2019). Nevertheless, this commonly used
94 **dichotomous** classification of sport modalities has been questioned.

95 Recently, two similar solutions have been proposed to overcome a **mere OSS-CSS**
96 **dichotomy** (Heilmann et al., 2022; Shi et al., 2022) by splitting each category into two
97 new ones. One solution adds a further dimension of sequential (discrete) vs. continuous
98 (cyclic) motor skills to both OSS and CSS (Shi et al., 2022). The other creates four
99 categories as a function of environmental variability and predictability (Heilmann et al.,
100 2022). Category 1 includes CSS that are primarily cyclic in their execution and do not
101 present environmental changes during practice (e.g., running). Category 2 includes CSS,
102 in which the environment can offer different variations which, however, are known in
103 advance and can be implemented in previous training programs (e.g., **skeet and trap**
104 **shooting disciplines**). Category 3 includes OSS, in which athletes can anticipate different
105 environmental conditions to a limited extent (e.g., skiing). Category 4 includes OSS
106 sports in which the environmental variability challenges the ability to foresee the
107 situations that will arise and thus anticipate (e.g., combat and team sports).

108 The results of reviews **of evidence on the sport-cognition relation that exclusively**
109 **focus on or encompass the developmental years** depict a nuanced pattern of effects of
110 different sport modalities on various cognitive functions (Heilman et al., 2022) moderated
111 by age across the lifespan (Gu et al., 2019). **The focus on age is especially relevant when**
112 **considering that most of the existing reviews (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2021; Heilmann et**
113 **al., 2022; Shi et al., 2022) mainly address executive functions (EFs), which exhibit**
114 **differential developmental sequences** during childhood and adolescence (Anderson,
115 2001; Shaffer & Kipp, 2014). **EF is a multi-component construct comprising several**

116 interrelated cognitive processes responsible for controlling and organizing goal-directed
117 behaviors. Under this umbrella term, three core EFs are commonly identified (Diamond,
118 2013): (1) Working memory (WM): Actively updating, supervising, and replacing the
119 information held in mind (2) Inhibition or inhibitory control (IC): Ensuring the control of
120 the individual's attention, thoughts, emotions, and behaviors, as well as the suppression
121 of cognitive and behavioral tendencies caused by internal or external distractions. (3)
122 Cognitive flexibility (CF): Rapid adaption to new demands and rules within rapidly
123 changing situations. Certain EFs seem to develop earlier and at a faster pace than others
124 and most EFs undergo accelerated development in childhood, but exhibit continued
125 improvement through adolescence and into young adulthood (Best & Miller, 2010;
126 Ferguson et al., 2021; Huizinga et al., 2006). Considering these developmental
127 trajectories of EFs, the outcomes of the recent reviews on the sport-EF relation in children
128 and adolescents (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2021; Heilmann et al., 2022; Shi et al., 2022)
129 are hardly comparable.

130 Moreover, differences in the considered study design and sport modality limit the
131 comparability across reviews. The cross-sectional design of most of the reviewed studies
132 does not allow for drawing definitive conclusions on the causality of sport-type effects
133 on cognition (Gu et al., 2019; Heilmann et al., 2022), whereas only a minority addresses
134 causality with an interventional approach (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2021; Heilmann et al.,
135 2022). The review by Shi et al. (2022) focuses on interventional studies but broadly
136 encompasses sport and non-sport open and closed skills activities. Lastly, most of the
137 intervention studies included in the available reviews have a chronic design, meaning that
138 they investigated the longer-lasting effects of sports programs that extended over weeks
139 or months (Gu et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2022).

140 The added value of this systematic review is that of furthering our understanding

141 of the role of sport modality in the expected effects of sports practice on cognition by a)
142 overcoming the traditional dichotomous classification between the OSS and CSS; b)
143 focusing exclusively on interventional research to address causality; c) distinguishing the
144 acute and chronic effects of sport practice on cognitive outcomes; d) investigating the
145 possible moderating role of age, fitness level, and training experience.

146 **Methods**

147 *Registration of Systematic Review*

148 This systematic review was carried out according to PRISMA guidelines (Page et al.,
149 2021). Moreover, the original protocol was registered in the International Prospective
150 Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), being accepted with registration number
151 CRD42021261864, dated 23 August 2021.

152 *Literature Search*

153 The search was made in Web of Science, Scopus, Pubmed (MEDLINE), and Sport Discus
154 databases. It was limited to works published between the first of January 2013 and 12
155 August 2022 and to studies carried out in humans. Alerts in the different databases were
156 generated to determine whether a new publication of interest for our review was
157 incorporated. The searching strategy was repeated to review the new publications to
158 include those that met the inclusion criteria. In addition, the references of other previous
159 related reviews or meta-analyses and those of the selected studies were reviewed to find
160 eventual additional studies of interest that might not have appeared in the database search.

161 Three dimensions were established to select the keywords: cognitive functions
162 (dependent variable), sport modality (independent variable) and population. A series of
163 keywords were included for each of these keyword sets, combined using different

164 Boolean operators: (*Cognition* OR ‘*executive function**’ OR ‘*decision making*’ OR
165 ‘*cognitive function**’ OR ‘*inhibitory control*’ OR ‘*working memory*’ OR ‘*cognitive*
166 *flexibility*’ OR ‘*emotional intelligence*’ OR ‘*emotion regulation*’ OR ‘*delayed*
167 *gratification*’ OR ‘*delay of gratification*’) AND (‘*exercise type*’ OR ‘*exercise mode*’ OR
168 *sport** OR ‘*open skill**’ OR ‘*closed skill**’) AND (*child** OR *adolescent** OR *teen** OR
169 ‘*young adulthood*’).

170 ***Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria***

171 Studies that met the following inclusion criteria were considered: (1) those available in
172 English; (2) those submitted to a blind peer-review process; (3) studies whose population
173 was healthy, without any physical or mental disorder and not submitted to medical
174 treatment during the study; (4) studies developed with participants between 6 and 25 years
175 old; (5) studies with an intervention program focused on the acute or chronic effect caused
176 by the sports practice; (6) studies comparing different PA modalities implying, at least in
177 one of the experimental conditions, the practice of some sports mode; and (7)
178 interventions which involved the actual practice of PA and not motor imagery practice,
179 neither in laboratory conditions.

180 Studies in which the participants' environmental, metabolic, cognitive,
181 motivational or emotional conditions during the experimental sessions (e.g., hypoxia or
182 fasting until the start of the experimental condition) were altered were excluded. When
183 the information described in a study raised doubts about applying a criterion, the main
184 authors were contacted by e-mail before the final decision on inclusion/exclusion.

185 ***Study Selection***

186 The search was undertaken independently by two researchers (AGC and JJM). The

187 research papers were downloaded in Endnote, where the duplicates were removed. Then
188 the titles and abstracts of the different publications were reviewed, followed by the full
189 texts, to assess their possible inclusion. In case of doubt or disagreement, they were
190 resolved by discussion and, if needed, an additional researcher was consulted to reach a
191 consensus.

192 ***Data Extraction***

193 Two of the authors (AGC and JJM) carried out data extraction according to what was
194 established in consensus. The publications were classified according to whether the study
195 had a chronic or acute design. Once the previous step was completed, the extraction
196 focused on the following aspects: (1) author and publication year; (2) origin of the sample;
197 (3) sample size and sex at birth of participants; (4) age of participants; (5) socioeconomic
198 status; (6) training experience; (7) regular physical activity level; (8) characteristics of the
199 intervention program. These latter included: (a) sport modality (following the
200 classifications described by Heilmann et al. (2022); (b) overall duration (for acute
201 interventions: sum of session duration and time between sessions; for chronic
202 interventions: overall intervention duration in weeks/months and number of weekly
203 sessions); (c) session duration, (d) qualitative characteristics of the interventions; (e)
204 intensity; (8) cognitive assessments (following the categorization made by Pontifex et al.
205 (2019); (9) main results obtained, referring to the effects on the cognitive domains in
206 terms of improvement, decrease or absence of effects evaluated in each intervention
207 program.

208 **Quality Assessment**

209 Two authors (AGC and JJM) independently assessed the methodological quality of the
210 selected studies according to the Physiotherapy Evidence Database (PEDro) scale. In case

211 of disagreement, a third author (DCV) was consulted until an agreement was reached
212 between the authors. In assessing the methodological quality of studies, the PEDro scale
213 has been commonly used. It consists of 11 items that reliably assess randomization,
214 intention to treat, blinding, between-group comparison and measures of variability
215 (Maher et al., 2003). In conducting the assessment, an additional criterion (criterion 1)
216 relating to external validity (or "generality" or "applicability" of the trial) was retained for
217 completeness of the Delphi list. However, this criterion was not used to calculate the final
218 score. Following Zheng et al. (2021), the studies employing a within-subject design were
219 automatically awarded a point for the baseline comparability item. The item for blinded
220 subjects is given 0 points for all studies since the blinding of participants is not possible
221 in exercise behavioral intervention studies.

222 The included studies scored between 3 and 6 points, indicating poor or moderate
223 quality (Maher et al., 2003). All results of the methodological quality assessment of the
224 30 included studies are shown in Table 1.

225 [TABLE 1 NEAR HERE]

226 **Results**

227 *Search Results*

228 A total of 8,201 studies were found, reduced to 5,851 after duplicate removal, 143 after
229 title and abstract screening, and 25 after full-text screening. Further, five studies identified
230 from the references of previous systematic reviews and meta-analyses were added. Finally,
231 30 studies were included in this systematic review (Figure 1). Two authors performed this
232 selection process independently (AGC; JJM).

233 [FIGURE 1 NEAR HERE]

234 *Study Characteristics*

235 The search strategy provided 30 studies. Ten studies (33.3%) reported an acute
236 intervention with 557 participants, and 20 (66.6%) reported a chronic intervention with
237 2276 participants. Seven of the first ten studies were with interventions of category 4
238 OSS, 1 of category 1 CSS, and two on both. Of the 20 chronic effect studies, 14 had
239 interventions of category 4 OSS, 2 of category 1 CSS, 1 of category 2 CSS, and two
240 included sport modalities of categories 2 and 4. For more detailed information on the
241 characteristics of the included studies, see Table 2 (participant characteristics), 3 (acute
242 interventions), and 4 (chronic interventions).

243 **Demographic characteristics.** Concerning sex at birth, twenty-six studies (86.6%) were
244 conducted with male, and twenty-five studies (83.3%) with female participants. Only two
245 studies did not report the sex of the participants (Gallotta et al., 2015; Tallent et al., 2017).
246 None of the included studies did evaluate differences between sexes for cognitive
247 variables.

248 [TABLE 2 NEAR HERE]

249 *Acute effects*

250 Regarding the acute effect of sport modalities on cognitive performance, benefits have
251 been found in categories 1 (cyclical CSS) and 4 (combat and team OSS). **Only two acute**
252 **effect studies addressed the moderating role by fitness and no study addressed the**
253 **moderating role by training experience.**

254 *Effect of sports practice: Comparison between sports practice and no-sport condition*

255 The following results were found in studies comparing a sport intervention with a no-
256 sport condition. A positive effect on IC could be seen in five studies with category 4 OSS

257 (basketball, football, badminton; Cooper et al., 2018; Lind et al., 2019; Takahashi et al.,
258 2019, 2020; Wen et al., 2021), and in one study with category 1 CSS (Zumba-dance;
259 Peruyero et al., 2017). There was no differential effect on IC in only one study with
260 category 4 OSS (football; Williams et al., 2020). A positive effect on WM could be seen
261 in 2 studies with category 4 OSS (basketball and football; Cooper et al., 2018; Wen et al.,
262 2021). A positive effect on attention could be seen in two studies with category 4 OSS
263 (basketball; Cooper et al., 2018; Gallotta et al., 2015). No differential effect on memory
264 could be seen in only one study with category 4 OSS (football; Lind et al., 2019). A
265 negative effect on psychomotor processing accuracy emerged in only one category 4 OSS
266 with a pre-post design (cricket; Tallent et al., 2017).

267 *Effect of sport modality: Comparison between different sports practice conditions*

268 Four studies compared different experimental conditions with category 1 and 4 sports
269 interventions. Two studies compared two sport modalities: basketball vs. running
270 (Gallotta et al., 2015) and running vs. badminton (Hung et al., 2018). Two other studies
271 compared a sport modality with PA conditions: badminton vs. treadmill running
272 (Takahashi & Grove, 2019) and badminton vs. treadmill brisk walking vs. resistance
273 training (Takahashi & Grove, 2020). Studies comparing sport modalities reported that
274 those in category 4 OSS, compared to those in category 1 CSS, were more beneficial to
275 attentional performance (Gallotta et al., 2015), reaction time (Hung et al., 2018) and IC
276 (Takahashi & Grove, 2019, 2020).

277 *Moderation by age: subgroup synthesis*

278 **Studies in childhood (between 6 and 10 years of age).** Two studies were found for this
279 age range. One of them found gains in IC and WM when participants performed a
280 category 4 OSS (football; Wen et al., 2021). Also, in another study with category 1 CSS

281 intervention (endurance training) and category 4 OSS (basketball) interventions,
282 improvements in the D2-Attention Test were found as compared to a general PA
283 intervention without any sports practice, and were more pronounced for the category 4
284 OSS as compared to the category 1 CSS intervention (Gallotta et al., 2015).

285 **Studies in late childhood and adolescence (between 11 and 16 years of age).** Three
286 studies were found for this age range. All of them developed category 4 OSS interventions
287 but with different results. Two studies found a positive effect on IC (basketball; Cooper
288 et al., 2018; football; Lind et al., 2019). Another one (football; Williams et al., 2020)
289 found no enhancement of IC but an improvement in WM; conversely, WM did not
290 achieve progress in Lind et al. (2019) study (football). Regarding CF, Cooper et al. (2018)
291 found gains only in adolescents with better physical fitness. Only one study showed
292 attention improvements (football; Lind et al., 2019).

293 **Studies in late adolescence and young adulthood (between 16 and 25 years).** For this
294 age range, five studies were found. A positive effect on IC was found in three studies
295 (Zumba; Peruyero et al., 2017; badminton; Takahashi & Grove, 2019, 2020). Another
296 study showed increased CF (in favor of badminton vs. running; Hung et al., 2018).
297 Finally, a deterioration in psychomotor processing accuracy was reported in only one
298 study (cricket; Tallent et al., 2017).

299 *Moderation by fitness and training experience*

300 *Only two studies tested moderation by fitness of the acute sport-cognition relation,*
301 *comparing a category 4 OSS bout with a resting condition (Cooper et al., 2018; Williams*
302 *et al., 2020). The higher-fit participants, compared to their lower-fit counterparts, showed*
303 *a transient benefit to WM (Williams et al., 2020), or a benefit to IC performance that did*
304 *not change into a deterioration over time as it did in the lower-fit group (Cooper et al.,*

305 2018). Further, three studies reported either the fitness level or the training experience
306 without addressing the moderation by these factors.

307 *Moderation by cognitive outcome, variable and assessment measure*

308 Further subgroup syntheses to identify moderation of intervention effects by cognitive
309 outcome, variable and assessment measure are reported in Supplementary Material 1.

310 *Summary*

311 In summary, transient cognitive performance gains after single bouts of sports activities
312 emerged at all ages. Among studies comparing the effects of a sport bout with a resting
313 condition, the cognitive variables studied (mainly IC and WM) improved regardless of
314 the type of intervention applied (cyclic and combat/team sports). Some studies with sports
315 interventions of the same category did not converge on the same results for the same
316 cognitive functions. For example, Cooper et al. (2018) and Williams et al. (2020)
317 analyzed the effects of an acute bout of category 4 OSS on IC, but only the first found
318 positive results. The only negative result was found in a study with young adults limited
319 to a non-executive function (psychomotor processing accuracy; Tallent et al., 2019).
320 Among studies comparing the acute effects of different sport modalities, a differential
321 effect on IC in favor of category 4 OSS (badminton) compared to Category 1 CSS
322 (running) could be seen in two studies (Takahashi et al., 2019, 2020). No differential
323 effect on WM could be seen in the only one study with category 4 OSS (football)
324 compared to category 1 CSS (resistance training; Wen et al., 2021). A differential effect
325 on CF in favor of category 4 OSS (badminton) compared to category 1 (running) could
326 be seen in one study (Hung et al., 2018). A differential effect on attention in favor of
327 category 4 (basketball) compared to category 1 CSS (resistance training) and in favor of

328 category 1 CSS (endurance training) compared to no sport could be seen in one study
329 (Gallotta et al., 2015).

330 [TABLE 3 NEAR HERE]

331 *Chronic effects*

332 Regarding the chronic effect of sport modalities on cognitive performance, benefits have
333 been found with both OSS and CSS interventions. Only one of the chronic effect studies
334 addressed the moderating role by training experience, and no study addressed the
335 moderating role by fitness.

336 *Effect of sports practice: Comparison between sports practice and no-sport condition*

337 Regarding the studies comparing the effect of a sport intervention with a control condition
338 (sedentary group), category 4 OSS interventions enhanced IC (Alesi et al., 2016; Cho et
339 al., 2017; Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022; Pesce et al., 2016), WM (Alesi et al., 2016;
340 Chiroso Rios et al., 2016; Shi et al., 2021), CF (Chiroso Rios et al., 2016; Lo et al., 2019;
341 Schmidt et al., 2015; Venckunas et al., 2016), decision making (Condello et al., 2021)
342 and attention (Alesi et al., 2015, 2016; Lind et al., 2018). Category 1 CSS interventions
343 improved IC, CF (Zinelabidine et al., 2022), and WM (Hsieh et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2021;
344 Zinelabidine et al., 2022). One category 2 CSS intervention boosted semantic fluency
345 (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022).

346 *Effect of sport modality: Comparison between different sports practice conditions*

347 Four studies were selected. One study compared two different sport modalities (handball
348 and athletics) and found differential benefits of handball to IC but athletics to semantic
349 fluency (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022). Further, two studies compared two versions

350 (volleyball: Formenti et al., 2019) or two dosages (tennis; Ishihara & Mizuno, 2018) of
351 the same sports modality and found selective gains in IC and WM, respectively. A third
352 study contrasted two higher-intensity interventions, one made of a mix of two category 4
353 OSSs (floorball/basketball) and one 1 CSS (aerobic exercise), and a low-intensity and
354 cognitively low-challenge PA condition (Schmidt et al., 2015), reporting a differential
355 effect on CF in favor of the category 4 OSS compared to the category 1 CSS and low
356 demanding PA conditions.

357 *Moderation by age: subgroup synthesis*

358 **Studies in childhood (between 6 and 10 years of age).** A positive effect on IC could be
359 seen in three studies: Two with category 4 OSS interventions (football; Chang et al., 2013;
360 tennis; Ishihara & Mizuno, 2018) and one with a category 1 CSS intervention (aerobic
361 dance; Zinelabidine et al., 2022). Further five studies showed positive effects on WM of
362 sports interventions, two of which with category 4 OSS (football; Alesi et al., 2016;
363 tennis; Ishihara & Mizuno, 2018) and three with category 1 CSS (gymnastics; Hsieh et
364 al., 2017; Lin et al., 2021; aerobic dance; Zinelabidine et al., 2022). Only one study did
365 not report gains in IC or WM with a category 4 OSS intervention (football and basketball;
366 Condello et al., 2021). Three studies showed positive effects on CF of sports
367 interventions, two with category 4 OSS (tennis; Ishihara & Mizuno, 2018), and one with
368 category 1 CSS (aerobic dance; Zinelabidine et al., 2022). Two studies showed
369 improvements in visual discrimination after a category 4 OSS intervention (football;
370 Alesi et al., 2015, 2016). However, Alesi et al. (2015) did not report gains in selective
371 attention. One study found a gain in decision-making with a sports intervention with
372 category 4 OSS (football and basketball; Condello et al., 2021).

373 **Studies in late childhood and adolescence (between 11 and 16 years of age).** A
374 positive effect on IC could be seen in four studies, three of which with category 4 OSS
375 interventions (taekwondo; Cho et al., 2017; handball; Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022;
376 volleyball; Formenti et al., 2019) and one study with categories 1 CSS and 4 OSS
377 interventions (multisport; Pesce et al., 2016). Further three studies achieved
378 enhancements in WM with category 4 OSS interventions (football, basketball, and
379 handball; Chiroso-Rios et al., 2016; football; Lind et al., 2018; football, basketball, and
380 handball; Martín-Martínez et al., 2015). Regarding CF, three studies with category 4 OSS
381 interventions improved CF performance assessed through different tests (football,
382 basketball, and handball; Chiroso-Rios et al., 2016; judo; Lo et al., 2019; football,
383 basketball, and handball; Martín-Martínez et al., 2015). Finally, advancements in
384 attention, perceptual and reaction speed could be observed in two studies with category 4
385 OSS interventions (attention: football; Lind et al., 2018); perceptual and reaction speed:
386 volleyball; Formenti et al., 2019).

387 **Studies in late adolescence and young adulthood (between 16 and 25 years).** One
388 study with a category 4 OSS intervention showed enhanced WM (football; Shi et al.,
389 2021), while another showed a beneficial effect of category 2 OSS (track and field;
390 Venckunas et al., 2016) on CF but not on WM. The available data shows that sports
391 interventions in childhood, late childhood, and adolescence similarly influenced IC and
392 WM. Nevertheless, due to heterogeneity in the cognitive tasks used to assess the same
393 cognitive function and the different interventions applied, it is impossible to check if age
394 could be a moderator in the causal relation between sport-based interventions and
395 improvements in cognitive performance.

396 *Moderation by fitness and training experience*

397 None of the selected chronic sports studies addressed the eventual moderation of the
398 effects of the sports program on cognitive function by the participant's fitness. Only one
399 study addressed and found a moderation by the participants' **training** experience, with
400 inexperienced children exhibiting the largest cognitive (decision making) gains after a
401 multisport program composed of category 4 OSS.

402 **Most studies reported the experience level but did not enter it into analysis as a potential**
403 **moderator. These interventions range from sport games (football, basketball, handball,**
404 **volleyball) and combat sports (taekwondo, judo) to track and field and dance.** The only
405 regularity that emerged is that in most studies, sedentary or low-expert participants were
406 recruited.

407 *Moderation by cognitive outcome, variable and assessment measure*

408 **Further subgroup syntheses to identify moderation of intervention effects by cognitive**
409 **outcome, variable and assessment measure are reported in Supplementary Material 1.**

410 *Summary*

411 In sum, both OSS and CSS interventions, with a major presence of category 4 OSS
412 interventions, benefited cognitive performances at all ages. Indeed, all studies showed
413 differential improvements in the sport intervention and comparator group at least in one
414 EF, attention, or non-executive function performance. Nevertheless, not all studies
415 measured and obtained benefits for all core EFs (IC, WM, and CF). While different sports
416 interventions benefited WM and CF across all considered age groups (in five and four
417 studies, respectively), specifically category 4 OSS interventions conducted in childhood
418 and adolescence also benefited IC (five studies), as well as decision-making, attention,
419 planning and visual discrimination, perceptual and reaction speed (four studies). The
420 fewer available category 1 CSS interventions boosted IC, WM and CF in children (Hsieh

421 et al., 2017; Zinelabidine et al., 2022), and one study with category 2 CSS interventions
422 boosted semantic fluency (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022).

423 Among studies comparing the effects of a sport intervention with a no-sport
424 condition, the majority (ten studies) found sport-related gains in EFs with a prevalence of
425 category 4 OSS interventions, with one study investigating decision-making (Condello et
426 al., 2021). Three studies investigated and found gains in attention (Alesi et al., 2015,
427 2016; Lind et al., 2018). Among studies comparing the chronic effects of different sport
428 modalities, core EFs (IC, WM, CF) benefited only or more pronouncedly from category
429 4 OSS compared to category 1 CSS (Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022; Schmidt et al., 2015)
430 or from more demanding versions of category 4 OSS compared to less demanding ones
431 (Formenti et al., 2019; Ishihara & Mizuno, 2018).

432 [TABLE 4 NEAR HERE]

433 **Discussion**

434 This systematic review aimed to further our understanding of the role of sport modality
435 in the expected transient (acute) and longer-term (chronic) effects of sports practice on
436 cognition by overcoming the traditional dichotomous classification between OSS and
437 CSS. This review also explored nuances of the causal sport-cognition relation by
438 analyzing the possible moderating role of individual characteristics (participants' age,
439 fitness level, and training experience). Further subgroup syntheses as a function of
440 cognitive outcome types and tasks used to measure them are also reported in a
441 supplementary file.

442 Overall, most of the sports practice interventions included (other than Tallent et
443 al., 2019) benefited cognitive performance in the short (acute effect) or the long term
444 (chronic effect). This review showed that some EFs are specifically benefited by sports

445 sharing common features such as complex skill acquisition, time pressure, and strategic
446 team actions. Improvements were found in different cognitive domains independently of
447 the participant's age. Few studies reported differences between groups regarding fitness
448 or training experience. However, none of them analyzed the joint role of these individual-
449 level moderators with task-level moderators, as PA dose tailored to the participants'
450 fitness or skill level (Herold et al., 2021).

451 *Acute Effect Studies*

452 In the **selected studies with acute design**, strategic OSS (category 4) were employed more
453 frequently than other sport modalities, **with positive** after-effects compared to no activity
454 on at least one EF and no adverse effects on any EF. Among the three core EFs, there was
455 a prevalence of studies focusing and reporting beneficial effects on inhibition and
456 working memory. Apart from only one study showing an absence of effect on inhibitory
457 control (Williams et al., 2020), few cases **reporting no** effects (Lind et al., 2019) or a
458 negative effect (Tallent et al., 2019) regarded non-executive functions (memory and
459 accuracy in psychomotor speed, respectively).

460 In studies that compared an acute bout of sports activity with a resting condition
461 (no activity), the superior cognitive performance observed after the sport bout can simply
462 reflect, at least partially, the arousing effect of the PA component of the sport bout. PA
463 bouts trigger several physiological alterations linked to enhanced arousal levels (Langner
464 & Eickhoff, 2013). In turn, exercise-induced arousal enhances **cognitive processes, with**
465 **the arousing benefits not limited to submaximal exercise intensity but also extending to**
466 **high-intensity exercise that can still benefit EF (Lambourne & Tomporowski, 2010;**
467 **Moreau & Chou, 2019).**

468 In the present review, the studies that contrasted different sport modalities showed
469 univocally that a bout of cognitively challenging, strategic OSS activity exerts a more

470 pronounced benefit than a bout of cyclic CSS activity on inhibitory control, attention, and
471 reaction speed. Most frequently and consistently, positive outcomes regard inhibitory
472 control, similar to what was found for acute aerobic PA in Verburgh et al.'s (2014) meta-
473 analysis. Interestingly, the comparisons between sport modalities in the studies included
474 in the present review were made exclusively between the two extremes of the open skills-
475 closed skills continuum, likely to exploit the maximum possible difference in cognitive
476 demands.

477 This advantage of strategic OSS to transiently act as 'cognitive boosters' confirms
478 the cognitive stimulation hypothesis that has been proposed to explain the differential
479 effects of different types of physical or sports activities on cognitive performance (Pesce,
480 2012). However, at developmental age, the pattern of results on the effects of single bouts
481 of cognitively engaging PA is mixed and suggests a joint influence of individual-level
482 moderators as age and task-level moderators as the cognitive complexity of the movement
483 task (Pesce, Ballester, et al., 2021). Some studies show that a highly cognitively
484 challenging bout of PA might be excessive and represent "too much of a good thing" for
485 children (Egger et al., 2018, p. 178) but an optimal challenge for adolescents (Benzing et
486 al., 2016). Other studies, instead, show that when the high cognitive challenge is
487 embedded in an enjoyable and playful PA (Jäger et al., 2014), also children can have
488 beneficial effects on inhibitory control, and can benefit even most from the highest level
489 of cognitive challenge (Anzeneder et al., 2023). In our review, the beneficial after-effects
490 of the cognitively challenging strategic OSS bouts were found across all considered ages
491 but were most consistent in studies with children.

492 The present review could not confirm the differential effects of acute bouts of OSS
493 and CSS on different EFs found in a previous systematic review that synthesized the
494 outcomes of acute interventional studies separately from those of chronic studies (Shi et

495 al., 2022). Shi and colleagues found that open skills are more beneficial to working
496 memory and cognitive flexibility, but closed skills to inhibitory control. We, in contrast,
497 found that strategic OSS were superior in transiently enhancing inhibitory control
498 compared to cyclic CSS. However, the partially different categorization of sport
499 modalities and age ranges considered does not allow for a thorough comparison.
500 Moreover, among the three core EFs, inhibition is the most multifaceted one, including
501 interference control, inhibition of thoughts, and behavioral inhibition (Diamond, 2013).
502 Thus, test differences may have resulted in different aspects of inhibition assessed.

503 A further aim of this review was to look for the possible moderator role of
504 participants' age, fitness level, and training experience. We detected improvements in
505 cognitive (mainly EF) performance after any type of acute sport-based interventions at
506 all ages (with childhood being most represented in eight of ten studies), suggesting that
507 there could not be developmental stages in which specific cognitive functions are
508 differentially sensitive to acute PA. This finding is in line with the absence of moderation
509 by age also found, specifically for EFs, by Verburgh et al. (2014) and by Ludyga et al.
510 (2021) when performance accuracy in EF tasks was considered. Instead, age effects
511 emerged and diverged in two reviews when EF performance speed was **individually or**
512 **jointly considered with accuracy** (Chang et al., 2012; Ludyga et al., 2021). Unlike these
513 precedents, our review included only studies employing bouts of sports activities that do
514 not have merely the physical demands of a bout of aerobic PA.

515 Fitness has been recognized as a moderator of the acute exercise-cognition
516 relationship, irrespective of whether the sport modality is open or closed skills (Pesce,
517 2009). Two studies in the present review found that only higher-fit adolescents but not
518 their lower-fit counterparts could benefit from a bout of OSS to enhance their working
519 memory performance, as assessed immediately after the sport activity bout (Cooper et al.,

520 2018; Williams et al., 2020) and their inhibitory control 45-min after its cessation (Cooper
521 et al., 2018). In contrast, the meta-analysis by Ludyga et al. (2016) could not identify any
522 differential responsiveness of EF to acute aerobic exercise among participants with high,
523 moderate, or low fitness levels. Future studies should also consider not only the physical
524 fitness and sport expertise, but also the baseline cognitive developmental level. According
525 to Drollette et al. (2014), the poorest the performance before starting an intervention, the
526 bigger the sensitivity to single bouts of PA and the opportunity for the individual to
527 improve. Regrettably, none of the studies included in this systematic review addressed
528 this issue.

529 *Chronic Effect Studies*

530 Regarding the chronic effect of sport modalities on cognitive performance, benefits
531 have been found for both OSS and CSS intervention programs. However, similar to acute
532 studies, the majority of the interventions consisted of strategic OSS activities (category
533 4), a minority of cyclic CSS (category 1), and only one consisted of an intermediate
534 category (category 2). When comparing sports and control groups, all studies showed a
535 greater cognitive performance of those practicing sports in at least one cognitive outcome
536 regardless of the sports modality.

537 These overall effects of any sports program compared to not practicing any
538 structured sport training do not allow for disentangling the unique contribution of the
539 sport features from the unspecific effects of PA that may be subtended by structural and
540 functional brain changes triggered by enhanced cerebral blood flow and neurotransmitter
541 levels (Hillman et al., 2014; Valkenborgh et al., 2019; Voss et al., 2013). These
542 neurotrophic stimulation and cardiovascular fitness hypotheses have probably played a
543 role in the cognitive benefits of sports programs that we have found over a wide range of
544 cognitive outcomes, because cardiovascular activity is highly prevalent in sports, and

545 some training programs also reported fitness gains parallel to cognitive gains. Candidate
546 mechanisms by which PA may affect general plasticity in brain structure and function
547 during development have been suggested to be linked to the protracted development of
548 the prefrontal cortex and the neurogenic capacity of hippocampal areas (Kahn & Hillman,
549 2014). Evidence syntheses confirm this suggestion but also show broader effects on
550 various structures involved in functional networks in frontal and parietal regions, anterior
551 cingulate cortex, hippocampus, and several white matter tracts (Valkenborghs et al.,
552 2019).

553 However, not every type of PA impacts the same brain regions, as the loci of the
554 cardiovascular and coordinative exercise effects differ (Voelcker-Rehage et al., 2013).
555 Indeed, coordinative PA involving motor learning activates structural and functional
556 brain plasticity that is more localized and specifically related to the learning experience
557 and skills learned (Adkins et al., 2006; Dayan & Cohen, 2011). Since the initial stage of
558 motor learning poses higher cognitive demands, the beneficial effects prevalent in the
559 studies selected for the present review suggest that complex motor learning in sports that
560 inherently involve cognitive challenge, activating the same brain regions to control
561 higher-order cognitive processes, makes sports practice an efficient means to enhance
562 cognitive abilities (Moreau et al., 2015; Tomporowski & Pesce, 2019). This supports the
563 ‘cognitive stimulation hypothesis’.

564 Our results showed that OSS interventions benefit EFs, attention, planning,
565 perceptual and reaction speed. The time constraints posed by strategic OSS mean that
566 players have to plan, anticipate, make decisions, and execute actions very quickly and
567 therefore require – and develop through practice - efficient cognitive functions (Walsh,
568 2014). However, not just OSS involve a combination of PA and cognitive engagement;
569 the gymnastics interventions included in this review (Hsieh et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2021)

570 showed evidence of beneficial chronic effects specifically on working memory. These
571 findings fit with evidence that dance, a highly demanding coordinative activity that,
572 similarly to gymnastics, involves the need to memorize long and complex movement
573 sequences, specifically increases memory capacity and the volume of hippocampal and
574 parahippocampal structures underlying memory functions (Teixeira-Machado et al.,
575 2019). Unfortunately, in the present review, interventions falling in the CSS categories
576 were strongly underrepresented, and those of the category 3 OSS with only partially
577 predictable environmental changes were absent, thus not allowing to draw **more**
578 **generalizable** conclusions.

579 Only a few studies compared different sports training modalities in the same
580 experiment. The two studies that compared strategic OSS with CSS programs found a
581 gain in EFs (inhibitory control and cognitive flexibility) for children and early adolescents
582 trained with the more cognitively challenging OSS program (Contreras-Osorio et al.,
583 2022; Schmidt et al., 2015). This suggests that OSS acts as a specific training of those
584 EFs due to the demands to flexibly change the criteria to cope with the ongoing game
585 situation (cognitive flexibility) and identify task-relevant information limiting the
586 interference of distracting stimuli (inhibitory control). Interestingly, while for the cyclic
587 CSS comparator with the lowest cognitive demands, no cognitive gain was observed
588 (Schmidt et al., 2015), for the more variable CSS modality employed by Contreras-Osorio
589 et al. (2022), a gain was observed in a more general indicator of cognitive development
590 (semantic fluency). This means that the degree of variability in sport skill learning may
591 be a relevant feature to better differentiate the effects of OSS and CSS on cognition (Pesce
592 et al., 2019).

593 Lastly, also the overall dose of strategic OSS training (Ishihara & Mizuno, 2018)
594 and the dose of cognitive training specifically designed to add cognitive demands relevant

595 to the sports modality trained (Formenti et al., 2019) seem relevant to obtain EF gains.
596 Moreover, it is well known that the methodological proposals or learning tasks may have
597 different cognitive demands, so the impact of the activity on the brain could be different.
598 During the last decades, the teaching of OSS has experienced a growing tendency to
599 abandon the traditional decontextualized technical learning approach in favor of **more**
600 **ecological** tactic learning (Clark et al., 2019; Forrest 2013). These **emerging** approaches
601 could lead to different effects on cognitive function, so future research should consider
602 the moderating role of these variables.

603 **Also**, how physical educators/sports trainers deliver a sports training program can
604 moderate the impact it may have on cognition **via** emotional/motivational **processes**
605 **triggered by** strategies **that** stimulate athletes' participation, thinking, and learning
606 (Gréhaigne & Godbout, 2020). The role of expert deliverers in achieving a cognitive
607 engagement elicited by PA enriched with skill learning demands seems central to
608 obtaining gains in inhibition in children and adolescents (Álvarez-Bueno et al., 2017; De
609 Greeff et al., 2018; Vazou et al., 2019). Recently, Pesce, Vazou, et al.'s **meta-review**
610 (2021, p. 11) **concluded** that "PA intervention delivered by an expert in an ecological
611 learning setting would benefit executive function because experts are best suited to
612 customize the skill learning process and maintain an optimal challenge point, critical to
613 benefit executive function". Sadly, none of the studies of this systematic review reported
614 enough information about delivery process characteristics to better understand its possible
615 moderator effect.

616 As regards the possible moderating role of individual characteristics in the relation
617 between chronic sport training interventions and cognitive function, our results did not
618 allow us to identify age differences, consistently with recent meta-analytical evidence
619 (Ludyga et al., 2020). Also, the role of fitness **could not be evaluated** since none compared

620 groups with different fitness levels. Regarding the training experience, sedentary or low-
621 expert participants were mainly recruited, presumably to maximize the possibility of
622 obtaining training-related gains. Only in one study, **the moderation by previous expertise**
623 **was tested with a cross-over design** (Condello et al., 2021). Children with no training
624 experience **improved** decision-making **more** after the sports intervention than those with
625 prior experience. This highlights the relevance of baseline expertise levels for
626 determining the efficacy of a sports program to improve EF.

627 *Acute–Chronic Effect Linkage*

628 We consider it essential to address the possible relationship between the acute and chronic
629 effects of sport-based interventions. If repeated over time, will sports practice that induces
630 immediate cognitive benefits at an acute level continue generating **chronic** benefits? The
631 meta-analysis by Liu et al. (2020) indicates that acute and chronic PA may efficiently
632 improve EFs in healthy children and adolescents. Indeed, the effect of chronic, protracted
633 PA might equal the accumulative effect of single, acute bouts of PA.

634 One of the potential biological mechanisms underpinning both transient and
635 longer-lasting effects of PA/sport on brain and cognition is represented by enhanced
636 levels of circulating Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF). The increase in BDNF
637 concentration can be observed in response to various acute PA protocols and modalities
638 (Ferris et al., 2007), as well as an effect of BDNF isoforms over structural brain changes
639 has been observed in the long term (Lu et al., 2005). In our review, we have reported
640 evidence of changes in neurotrophins' concentration associated with cognitive
641 performance gains in response to single bouts of sport activity (Hung et al., 2018) as well
642 as to extended sport training programs (Cho et al., 2017). A further mechanism underlying
643 accumulated bouts of sports activities could be the modulation of white-matter integrity.
644 The changes in working memory and white matter integrity reported after OSS training

645 in early adulthood (Shi et al., 2021) are likely grounded in the association between
646 cardiovascular fitness, white matter integrity, and working memory efficiency that
647 emerges already in adolescence (Ruotsalainen et al., 2020).

648 Thus PA, which induces cognitive benefits at the acute level, may also induce
649 cognitive benefits at the chronic **level**. However, the optimal acute stimulation level to
650 induce long-term cognitive benefits still requires clarification. An acute impairment in
651 cognitive performance may trigger the adaptative response to the training, which induces
652 long-term improvements. For this reason, while long-term engagement in PA is critical
653 to inducing lasting changes, studying the short-term effects of exercise is still essential to
654 better understand mechanisms that benefit the change at different time scales (Moreau &
655 Chou, 2019).

656 ***Practical Application***

657 From the results obtained, as a practical application, we could highlight the improvement
658 in **EFs and attention skills that are crucial in** other contexts, such as school **learning**.
659 Several studies have observed a positive correlation between EFs and academic
660 achievement (Escolano-Pérez & Bestué, 2021; Gutiérrez-Ruiz et al., 2020), **as well as** the
661 predictive validity of motor coordination for EFs and the latter for academic achievement
662 **(e.g., Schmidt et al., 2017). This evidence** suggests the usefulness of letting children
663 engage in **sports**, which are both cognitively and coordinatively demanding and
664 physically engaging. On the other hand, the need to individualize the training process,
665 finely tuning the task demands to the individual skill level and resources (functional
666 difficulty), seems evident.

667 ***Limitations***

668 One of the aims of this systematic review was to detect subtle differences among the

669 effect of different sports modes overcoming the traditional dichotomous classification
670 between the OSS and CSS. Nevertheless, the heterogeneity among intervention features
671 challenged the studies' categorization, and the alternative classification by Heilmann et
672 al. (2022) does not seem sensitive enough to tap the most discriminant features of the
673 interventions. Moreover, because of the need to split studies into several categories of
674 sport modalities to address the study's central question, we did not address the issue of
675 heterogeneity of assessment tools in depth (Supplementary material 1) and merged the
676 outcomes from different measurements of the same cognitive function into the same
677 cognitive category. A systematic review of cognitive assessment in physical activity
678 research involving children and adolescents has highlighted the use of a too broad array
679 of tests and called for a convergence of a smaller number to improve the comparability
680 and interpretability of future research (Wade et al., 2020).

681 Moreover, while overall conclusions on the beneficial effects of acute and chronic
682 sport interventions for EFs could be drawn, their generalizability to the broader construct
683 of EF is limited by the fact that the included studies almost exclusively addressed 'cool'
684 EFs tested in a decontextualized manner. While potential confounding with sport-specific
685 skills is avoided in this way, this kind of affectively neutral testing is at odds with the
686 motivational salience of the ecological sport context in which EFs are trained. Future
687 studies should address 'hot' EF processes (Pesce, Stodden, et al., 2021) that are performed
688 in affectively salient contexts, such as making risky decisions with much to be gained or
689 lost (Zelazo & Carlson, 2012). Indeed, decision-making is the cognitive function that
690 exhibits the largest effect size in skilled athletes (Kalén et al., 2021) and seems sensitive
691 to a sport intervention in childhood, as suggested by the only study that assessed a 'hot'
692 decision-making outcome in this review.

693 Finally, the few available studies limited the possibility of examining some key

694 questions. However, the small number of studies also means that our review calls for
695 additional research and provides preliminary insights into the impact of sport on child
696 cognition to inform future research.

697 *Conclusion and outlook*

698 Regardless of modality, a sport generates cognitive benefits in the short and long
699 term. Such benefits vary among cognitive functions and domains, depending on the sport
700 modality practiced. This review showed broadly positive results, especially for higher-
701 level cognition (EFs) but also a few cases of absence of effects and one case of impairment
702 of **lower-level** cognition (psychomotor speed).

703 Regarding the role of individual-level moderators, **age did not emerge as a**
704 **discriminant factor, both because investigations in childhood were overrepresented**
705 **compared to adolescent and young adult studies, and because no substantial differences**
706 **in consistency of evidence were found among age classes.** Physical fitness was
707 investigated in only **two** acute studies and training experience in **only** one chronic study
708 **with** significant moderation in opposite directions. The acute study showed an amplifying
709 effect, meaning that a higher fitness level led to beneficial transient effects of the sport
710 bout. The chronic study showed a buffering effect, meaning that a higher baseline training
711 experience dampened the benefits of the sport intervention. **Thus, the role of individual-**
712 **level moderators warrants further research.**

713 Furthermore, a joint investigation of individual- and task-level moderators might
714 shed further light on acute and chronic sport effects on cognition (Pesce, 2009). The line
715 of sport and cognition research focused on the cognitive stimulation hypothesis might
716 rely on the *challenge point framework* (Akizuki & Ohashi, 2015; Guadagnoli & Lee,
717 2004). According to this framework, learning is directly related not to the task's nominal
718 difficulty but to the task's functional difficulty (how challenging the task is considering

719 the skill level of the person who performs it). Attempts to finely tune the ‘dose’ of
720 cognitive challenge to children’s skills that are emerging in recent acute PA research
721 (Anzeneder et al., 2023) may inform future sport and cognition research in order to fine-
722 tune sport interventions targeting the individually optimal challenge point and searching
723 for context-specific cognitive demands related to different sport modalities.

724 **Lastly**, it would be interesting to investigate this issue with a combined acute and
725 chronic design, with acute interventions embedded at the beginning and the end of a
726 chronic intervention. This approach might shed light on whether the practice of a sport
727 that produces immediate cognitive benefits or impairment translates into benefits when
728 this practice is repeated in the long term. This would mean that the chronic effect induced
729 by sports practice reflects resource mobilization at an optimal level to stimulate the
730 athlete's adaptive ability.

731 **Funding**

732 This study has been supported by grants awarded by the European Regional Development Fund
733 (ERDF) Andalusia Operational Programme 2014-2020 (Spanish Research Agency); SEJ-746-
734 UGR20 "Effect of the manipulation of contextual variables of physical exercise on mental load
735 and cognitive, emotional and athletic performance" and Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation
736 and Universities: Grant FPU19/06224 and Spanish Ministry of Universities: Grant
737 FPU20/02022.

738 **Acknowledgments**

739 The authors would like to thank Ángel Povedano Arévalo for his invaluable help.

740 **Disclosure statement**

741 No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

742 **Data Availability Statement**

743 The corresponding author had full access to all the data in the study.

744

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- 1072

1073 **Table 1.** PEDro scale for the 30 included studies.

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Total
Alesi et al., 2015				✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	5
Alesi et al., 2016				✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	5
Chang et al., 2013	✓	✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Chirosa et al., 2016		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Cho et al., 2017	✓	✓		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Condello et al., 2021		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022	✓			✓				✓		✓	✓	4
Cooper et al., 2018		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Formenti et al., 2019		✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Gallotta et al., 2015	✓	✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Hsieh et al., 2017	✓			✓				✓		✓	✓	4
Hung et al., 2018	✓							✓		✓	✓	3
Ishihara et al., 2018				✓						✓	✓	3
Latorre-Román et al., 2021		✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Lin et al., 2021	✓			✓				✓		✓	✓	4
Lind et al., 2018		✓						✓		✓	✓	4
Lind et al., 2019		✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Lo et al., 2019								✓	✓	✓	✓	4
Martín-Martínez et al., 2015		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Peruyero et al., 2017				✓				✓		✓	✓	4
Pesce et al., 2016		✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Schmidt et al., 2015		✓								✓	✓	3
Shi et al., 2021	✓	✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Takahashi et al., 2019		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Takahashi et al., 2020		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	6
Tallent et al., 2017								✓		✓	✓	3
Venckunas et al., 2016				✓						✓	✓	3
Williams et al., 2020		✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Xu et al., 2021	✓	✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5
Zinelabidine et al., 2022	✓	✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	5

Table 2. Characteristics of participants in the included studies.

Study	Country	Participant's N Male/Female	Year (age)	Socioeconomic Status	Training experience	Participant's regular physical activity level
Chang et al., 2013	Taiwan	N= 26 15/13	7.2 ± 0.3	Medium	Not reported	Not reported
Alesi et al., 2015	Italy	N= 46 Football (24): 24/0 Sedentary (22): 22/0	Football: 9.41 ± 0.96 Sedentary: 8.78 ± 1.13	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Gallotta et al., 2015	Italy	N= 116 Not reported Cognitive exertion group (39) Physical exertion group (31) cognitive plus physical exertion group (46)	Between 8-11 years old	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Marín-Martínez et al., 2015	Spain	N= 54 14/40	15.35 ± 0.48	Not reported	Sedentary population	Not reported
Schmidt et al., 2015	Switzerland	N= 181 Team games (69): 26/43 Aerobic exercise (57): 28/29 Control (55): 28/27	Team games: 11.32 ± 0.56 Aerobic exercise: 11.33 ± 0.61 Control: 11.40 ± 0.62	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Alesi et al., 2016	Italy	N=44 Football (24): 24/0 Sedentary (22): 22/0	Football: 8.78 ± 1.12 Sedentary: 9.25 ± 0.85	Medium	Novice players	Novice players
Chirosa et al., 2016	Spain	N= 39 CG (19): 0/19 EG (20): 0/20	15.41 ± 0.50	Not reported	No regular physical activity	Not reported
Pesce et al., 2016	Italy	N = 90 CG (45): 28/17 EG (45): 29/16	CG: 14.5 ± 0.5 EG: 14.5 ± 0.5	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Venckunas et al., 2016	Lithuania	N= 18 Sailors (8): 6/2 CG (10): 8/2	Sailors: 17.0 ± 1.1 CG: 17.5 ± 1.8	Not reported	Sailors: 3–4 years of training history CG: active lifestyle	Not reported
Cho et al., 2017	South Korea	N= 30 Taekwondo (15): 9/6 CG (15): 9/6	Taekwondo: 11.20 ± 0.77 CG: 11.33 ± 0.72	Not reported	Not reported	No regular exercise
Hsieh et al., 2017	Taiwan	N= 44 Gymnastics (24): 12/12 CG (20): 11/9	Gymnastics: 8.7 ± 1.1 CG: 8.6 ± 1.1	Medium to high	Not reported	Not reported
Peruyero et al., 2017	Spain	N= 44 23/21	16.39 ± 0.68	Medium	Experience in high-intensity activities	Not reported
Tallent et al., 2017	England	N= 8 Not reported	22 ± 3 years	Not reported	Professional cricket	Not reported
Cooper et al., 2018	United Kingdom	N= 39 20/19	12.3 ± 4.37	Not reported	Not reported	Low and high fitness level
Hung et al., 2018	Taiwan	N= 20 20/0	23.15 ± 2.48	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Ishihara et al., 2018	Japan	N= 106 52/54	9.9 ± 1.8	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Lind et al., 2018	Denmark	N= 931 Football (838): 410/428 Control (93): 40/53	11.9 ± 0.4	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Formenti et al., 2019	Italy	N= 51 0/51	Vision training group: 10.95 ± 0.71 Vision training sport-specific group: 11.13 ± 0.77 Context sport-specific group: 11.2 ± 0.73	Not reported	At least 4 years playing volleyball	Not reported

Table 2. Continued...

Lind et al., 2019	Denmark	N= 81 Small-sided real football games (27): 16/11 Small-sided walking football games (27): 16/11 Resting (27): 16/11	11.8 ± 0.2	Medium to high	Some participants had experience in football	Not reported
Lo et al., 2019	China	N= 29 EG (14): 11/3 CG (15): 11/4	EG: 13.36 ± 1.15 CG: 13.47 ± 1.24	Not reported	Physical activity program at school	Not reported
Takahashi et al., 2019	Japan	N= 20 8/12	20.9 ± 0.89	Not reported	Not reported	Unclear
Takahashi et al., 2020	Japan	N= 48 25/23	20.5 ± 1.39	Not reported	Not reported	Unclear
Williams et al., 2020	United Kingdom	N= 36 20/16	12.6 ± 0.5	Not reported	Not reported	Low and high fitness level
Condello et al., 2021	Italy	N= 181 EG (91): 46/45 CG (90): 45/45	EG: 10.73 ± 0.32 CG: 10.72 ± 0.31	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Latorre-Román et al., 2021	Spain	N= 114 EG (58): 29/29 CG (56): 31/25	EG: 9,76 ± 1,09 CG: 9,77 ± 1,11	Medium	Not reported	Not reported
Lin et al., 2021	Taiwan	N= 50 Gymnastic (26): 13/13 Wait-list CG (24): 13/11	Gymnastic: 8.5 ± 1.1 Wait-list CG: 8.7 ± 1.1	Medium to high	Not reported	Not reported
Shi et al., 2021	China	N= 111 CG (41): 24/17 EG (53): 38/15	CG: 18.49 ± 0.75 EG: 18.26 ± 0.52	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Wen et al., 2021	China	N= 145 Coordinative (35): 17/18 Resistance (41): 22/19 Football (32): 15/17 Control (37): 20/17	All: 10.9 ± 0.3 Coordinative: 10.9 ± 0.3 Resistance: 11.0 ± 0.31 Football: 10.9 ± 0.30 Control: 10.9 ± 0.4	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022	Spain	N= 90 Athletics (30): 16/14 Handball (30): 14/16 Control (30): 15/15	Athletics: 11.40 ± 0.85 Handball: 11.41 ± 0.59 Control: 11.45 ± 0.60	High	Any experience in handball or athletics sport	Not regular practice of physical exercise or sports for one or more days a week outside of the school context
Zinelabidine et al., 2022	Tunisia	N= 41 EG (19): 10/9 CG (22): 12/10	EG: 10.3 ± 0.57 CG: 10.03 ± 0.43	Medium	Not reported	Low physical activity level

Values are expressed as means ± standard deviations.

N, number of subjects; M, male; F, female; CG, control group; EG, experimental group.

Table 3. Interventions with Acute Design used by Included Studies.

Studies	Intervention program				Cognitive assessments	Outcomes	
	Sport Modality (Classification)	Length (Time between sessions)	Session Length	Description*	Intensity	Task [Domain of Cognition]	Results
Gallotta et al., 2015	Basketball (4) Endurance training (1)	1 session	50'	EG1: Continuous aerobic circuit training and submaximal shuttle run exercise EG2: Cognitive plus physical exertion (mini-games) EG3: academic class	MVI HR: > 139 bpm	d2-Test of Attention [Attention]	Medium to large size for the beneficial effect of physical education classes in AT. Improved performances in EG2 compared with EG1 and EG3
Peruyero et al., 2017	Zumba-Dance (1)	4 sessions	20'	EC1/EC2: Aerobic-Zumba: replicate movements EC3: Non-exercise (theoretical class)	EC1: LMI EC2: MVI	Stroop Task [Cognitive Control]	Practice Zumba at a MVI produce a higher effect in inhibition (Stroop Task) than at a LI
Tallent et al., 2017	Cricket (4)	Training session and match (Twenty20)	3 h	Tri-axial accelerometer during training and Twenty20	Not reported	Simple Reaction Time and accuracy [Motor Speed & Learning]	Twenty20 match and training increased error count
Cooper et al., 2018	Basketball (4)	3 sessions (7 days)	60'	EC: Basketball: Skill based drills and small sided games CC: Rest quietly whilst seated in a school classroom	HI combined with sitting	Stroop Task [Cognitive Control] Sternberg Task [Cognitive Control] Trail-Making-Test [Cognitive Control] d2-Test of Attention [Attention]	Games enhanced EF and WM in adolescents (particularly in fitter adolescents). They improved in response times in Stroop Task and Sternberg Task
Hung et al., 2018	Running (1) Badminton (4)	2 sessions (7 days)	35'	EC1: Running (run on an indoor track) EC2: Badminton (multi shuttle training)	CE1/CE2: 60% (\pm 5%) HRR	Task-Switching [Cognitive Control]	Badminton exercise resulted in near significant smaller global switching costs relative to running
Lind et al., 2019	Football (4)	1 session	30'	EG1: HI small - sided real football games EG2: MI small - sided walking football games CG: resting	EG1: HI (70–100% of HRR) EG2: MI (60–80% of HRR)	Flanker Task [Cognitive Control] Visual Memory Task [Memory] EEG [Neuroimaging]	MHI improved performance in IN compared to MI and task-related allocation of attention evidenced by changes in the P300 amplitude compared to MI and seated rest
Takahashi et al., 2019	Badminton (4)	4 sessions (5.8 days)	10'	EC1: Playing badminton singles games EC2: Ran on a treadmill CC: Rest (seated with their smartphones)	EC1: 75% VO2 peak EC2: 75% VO2 peak CC: Not reported	Stroop Task (Color word and reverse) [Cognitive Control]	Playing badminton has a greater impact on IN than running in a within-subjects design
Takahashi et al., 2020	Badminton (4)	5 sessions (4.5 days)	10'	EC1: Walked briskly (motor driven treadmill) EC2: Chest press, seated row and leg press EC3: Playing badminton (Singles game) CC: Rest (Seated with smartphones)	EC1: 6.0 km h ⁻¹ Speed EC2: 10 RM, 2x10 reps. + 30' rest (set/exercise) EC3: Not reported CC: Not reported	Stroop Task (Color word and reverse) [Cognitive Control]	Badminton (open-skilled exercise) has a significant interaction on IN (Stroop and Reverse Stroop tasks) compared with other closed-skilled exercise
Williams et al., 2020	Football (4)	3 sessions (7 days)	60'	EC1: Football (Skill based drills and SSG (5vs5; 30')) CC: Seated rest	Not reported	Stroop Task [Cognitive Control] Sternberg Task [Cognitive Control]	Football training has a significant interaction on WM only in the high-fitness group
Wen et al., 2021	Football (4)	1 session	40'	EG1 Soccer training: tackler, moving dribble, moving passing and catching, dribble shot EG2: Resistance training: ball tossing, push-up, and sit-up EG3: Coordinative training: rope skipping, shuttlecock CG: Watching cartoons	EG1: 122,3 bpm EG2: 118.8 bpm EG3: 121.1 bpm CG: 87,3 bpm	Go/No-Go Task [Cognitive Control] 2-Back [Cognitive Control]	Acute resistance, coordinative training, and football training with MI have positive impacts on the IN and WM. No differences between type of activities

AT, attention; BDNF, brain-derived neurotrophic factor; bpm, beats per minute; CC, control condition; CG, control group; EC, experimental condition; EF, executive function; EG, experimental group; HR, heart rate; HI, high intensity; HRR, heart rate reserve; IN, inhibition; LI, Light intensity; LMI, low to moderate intensity; MHI, moderate to high intensity; MI, moderate intensity; MVI, moderate to vigorous intensity; SSG, small-sided games; RPE, rate of perceived effort; WM, working memory.

*EC and CC refer to studies in which all participants are exposed to all experimental conditions (within-subjects design). EG and CG refer to studies in which each participant is only exposed to the experimental or control condition of their group (between-subjects design).

Table 4. Interventions with Chronic Design used by Included Studies.

Studies	Intervention program				Cognitive assessments		Outcomes
	Sport Modality (Classification)	Length (Weekly frequency)	Session Length	Description*	Intensity	Task [Domain of Cognition]	Results
Chang et al., 2013	Football (4)	8 weeks (2/week)	35'	EG1: Football's coordination movement in the lower extremities, and with continuous walking EG2: Football's coordination movement in the lower extremities, with continuous running	EG1: 40–50% HRmax EG2: 60–70% HRmax	Flanker Task (Modified Eriksen) [Cognitive Control]	Flanker task performance improved in both LI and MI
Alesi et al., 2015	Football (4)	24 weeks (2/week)	75'	EG1: Football exercise program (skills, technique or/and 1vs.1 and opposed games 3vs.3/ 5vs.5) CG: Not exercise group	Not reported	Visual Discrimination test [Attention] Visual Selective Attention test [Attention]	Visual discrimination times after the programme were improved by the football group compared to the sedentary group
Martin-Martinez et al., 2015	Football (4) Basketball (4) Handball (4)	8 weeks (2/week)	1 st : 60' 2 nd : 30'	1 st session: 10' x 6 SSG 3x3 (football (2), basketball (2) and handball (2)) 2 nd session: 10' x 3 SSG 3x3 (football (2), 2 basketball (2) and handball (2))	HR: 175.96 ± 10.26 bpm RPE: 13.36 ± 1.39	Trail-Making-Test [Cognitive Control] Digit Test & Letter and Number Test [Cognitive Control] Stroop Task [Cognitive Control] WISC [Intelligence & Achievement Tests]	Positive intervention effects were obtained on measures of WM (WISC Working Memory Index) and CF (time to complete Trail Making Test B)
Schmidt et al., 2015	Floorball (4) Basketball (4)	6 weeks (2/week)	45'	EG1: Team games (Floorball and Basketball) EG2: Aerobic exercise CG: Control condition	EG1/EG2: HI CG: LI	Flanker Task (Modified Eriksen) [Cognitive Control] N-Back [Cognitive Control]	The high physical exertion with enriched cognitive engagement found positive effects in CF but not in WM and IC
Alesi et al., 2016	Football (4)	6 months (2/week)	75'	EG1: Football Exercise program (individual skills, technique or/and 1vs.1 situation, opposed games involving 3vs.3 and 5vs.5) CG: Not exercise group	Not reported	Digit Span Tests [Cognitive Control] Corsi Block [Cognitive Control] Visual-spatial updating [Attention] Visual Discrimination task [Attention] Tower of London Task [Cognitive Control]	The football group at post-test showed significantly larger gains (significant differences) than the sedentary group on measures of visuo-spatial, WM, AT, planning and IN
Pesce et al., 2016	Multisport (2 and 4)	6 months (2/week)	60'	EG1: Intervention in multi-sport Physical Education EG2: Traditional Physical Education	Not reported	The Random Number Generation Task [Cognitive Control]	A multisports physical education setting has positive outcomes in IN
Chirosa et al., 2016	Football (4) Basketball (4) Handball (4)	8 weeks (3/week)	1 st : 60' 2 nd : 30'	1 st session: 10' x 6 SSG 3x3 (football (2), basketball (2) and handball (2)) 2 nd session: 10' x 3 SSG 3x3 (football (2), 2 basketball (2) and handball (2))	HR: 175.68 ± 11.39 bpm RPE 13.20 ± 1.53	Trail-Making-Test [Cognitive Control] Digit Test & Letter and Number Test [Cognitive Control] Stroop Task [Cognitive Control] WISC [Intelligence & Achievement Tests]	A positive impact of the physical activity programme applied to adolescent girls was found on the WISC WM Index (WISC-IV) and CF (Trail Making Test form B)
Venckunas et al., 2016	Track and field (2)	7 weeks (4/week)	42'–90'	EG: Interval running training program: 200m–1,000 m intervals with a progressive increase in the number of repetitions each week	HI increased 12' to 30' per session Practice HR: 190bpm Rest HR: 130 bpm	Schulte-Gorbov Test [Cognitive Control] Odd-even test [Cognitive Control] Free recall Task [Memory] Forward Digit-Span Task [Cognitive Control]	The interval running training cause benefits on CF tasks
Cho et al., 2017	Taekwondo (4)	16 weeks (5/week)	60'	EG: Taekwondo training CG: Not exercise condition	EG1: RPE: 11–15	StroopTask (Color word and reverse) [Cognitive Control]	Taekwondo training cause IN associated with Serum BDNF, VEGF, and IGF-1 higher levels that can induce an increase in neurotrophic factors and growth factors
Hsieh et al., 2017	Gymnastics (1)	8 weeks (2/week)	90'	EG: Gymnastic training CG: Not exercise condition	MI controlled by HR	Modified delayed matching- to-sample test [Memory]	Gymnastics training had a positive effect on spatial WM related to an increase in response accuracy in the modified delayed sample matching test and P3 amplitude
Ishihara et al., 2018	Tennis (4)	12 months EG1 (1/week) EG2 (4/week)	Not reported	EG1: 48 sessions EG2: 192 sessions Tennis lessons: The type of tasks performed, and the sessions time is not specified	MVI	StroopTask (Modified Eriksen) [Cognitive Control] 2-Back [Cognitive Control] Local-global Task [Cognitive Control]	IN, WM, and CF benefits were positively associated with frequent tennis practice and high MVI

Lind et al., 2018	Football (4)	11 weeks (2/week)	45'	EG: Intervention sessions (teaching soccer skills and playing small-sided soccer) CG: Regular physical education classes	EG: HIIT CG: Not reported	Detection & Identification Task [Attention] 1-Back [Cognitive Control] One card Learning [Cognitive Control]	HIIT based on football group improved their psychomotor function, AT and WM compared to the CG
Formenti et al., 2019	Volleyball (4)	6 weeks (2/week)	90'	EG1: Traditional volleyball training EG2: Training exercises combined with generic motor actions in a non-sport performance context EG3: Same as EG2, with one difference: The motor actions were not generic but specific to volleyball	Not reported	Simple Reaction Time [Motor Speed & Learning] Flanker Task [Cognitive Control] Visual Search Task [Attention]	Vision training in non-sport-specific context improved cognitive performance (reaction time, executive control, perceptual speed) but seems to be less effective for improving sport-specific skills
Lo et al., 2019	Judo (4)	8 weeks (3/week)	90'	Judo practice: Falling techniques (throw down, push down, and hook down), randori (judo fighting on the ground and standing judo fighting) EG1: judo players EG2: not judo players CG: Not intervention training	Not reported	Spatial Task-Switching Test [Cognitive Control]	The protocol for judo players and non-players revealed lower error rates on change trials compared to the CG. In addition, the judo group improved error rates from baseline to post-intervention compared to the CG
Condello et al., 2021	Football (4) Basketball (4)	6 months (1/week)	60'	EG: Intervention in enriched Physical Education (multisport centered on team games, life skills training, TGfU, and cognitive stimulation approach) CG: Traditional Physical Education	RPE: EG: 4.11 ± 3.10 CG: 1.27 ± 1.39	Cool EFs: The Random Number Generation Task [Cognitive Control] Hot EFs: GPAI: Decision Making and Support components	A multisport (team games) setting has positive outcomes in Decision Making (hot EF). In contrast IN and WM did not benefit (cool EFs)
Latorre-Román et al., 2021	Team Sports (4)	10 weeks (3/week)	30'	EG: Team games (e.g. football, basketball) CG: daily activities (differents exercise practiced by the EG)	EG: RPE 6.94 ± 2.18	Trail-Making-Test (A, B) [Cognitive Control] School Aptitude Test [Intelligence & Achievement Tests]	EG had greater benefits in all variables of school aptitudes and CF than CG
Lin et al., 2021	Gymnastic (1)	8 weeks (2/week)	90'	EG: Gymnastics training based on floor exercises, jumping box, gymnastic trampoline, balance beam, hurdle walking and forward parallel bars CG: Not intervention training	HR: 136.4 ± 16.8 bpm (68% of age predicted HRmax) RPE: 11.8 ± 1.8	Delayed-Matching Working Memory Task [Memory]	Gymnastics training has a positive effect in WM regardless of memory demands
Shi et al., 2021	Football (4)	10 weeks (7/week)	60'	Warm Up: running and freehand exercises Main part: Skills (soccer juggling games)	Not reported	N-Back [Cognitive Control]	Soccer juggling learning was able to improve WM and remodel WMI in early adulthood
Contreras-Osorio et al., 2022	Handball (4) Athletics (2)	12 weeks (4/week)	60'	EG1: Handball intervention (tasks, exercise or games combining the phases of the game) EG2: Athletics intervention: basic abilities and lifts, introduction to fartlek and continuous running EG3: Not exercise condition	MVI RPE: 5–7	Verbal Fluency [Intelligence & Achievement Tests] Trail-Making-Test [Cognitive Control] Ring Task [Memory] StroopTask [Cognitive Control]	Athletics intervention improved semantic fluency. Handball intervention improved IN.
Zinelabidine et al., 2022	Aerobic dance (1)	8 weeks (2/week)	45'	Aerobic dance practice (three dances of 10' each one)	First 6 sessions: 60–75% HRmax. 7 th –14 th sessions: 75–85% HRmax. 15 th –16 th sessions: 60–70% HRmax.	Trail-Making-Test [Cognitive Control] StroopTask [Cognitive Control] Digit Recall Test [Cognitive Control]	Intervention program based on 8 weeks of aerobic dance resulted in an improved CF, IN, and WM in comparison with the control group and the pre-intervention assessment

AT, attention; BDNF, brain-derived neurotrophic factor; bpm, beats per minute; CG, control group; EG, experimental group; HI, high intensity; HIIT, high intensity interval training; HR, heart rate; HRmax, Maximum heart rate; IGF-1, insulin-like growth factor 1; IN; inhibition; LI, low intensity; RPE, rating of perceived exertion; SSG, small-sided games; TGfU, teaching games for understanding; VEGF, vascular endothelial growth factor; WISC, Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children; WM, working memory.

*EC and CC refer to studies in which all participants are exposed to all experimental conditions (within-subjects design). EG and CG refer to studies in which each participant is only exposed to the experimental or control condition of their group (between subjects design).